

ADVENTIST MEDICAL CENTER COLLEGE
San Miguel, Iligan City

**PERCEIVED LANGUAGE BARRIERS TO
HEALTH CARE DELIVERY SYSTEM**

A thesis
presented in partial fulfillment
of the requirement for the degree
BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN NURSING

by

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Judelyn Angcap
Erika Mae E. Aragon
Norhanna D. Moner

August 2024

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DEDICATION

This research paper is dedicated to the parents of the researchers and for our research adviser Ma'am Armelyn Grace Maghanoy, for their unconditional love, endless support, sacrifices, and emotional support, and for always being there in rough and tough times. The encouragement and belief they gave motivated the researchers to aim higher.

The researchers are nothing without them, the beloved parents.

Lastly, the researchers humbly dedicate this work to the Almighty God for guiding us every step of the way.

Fa Inna ma'al 'usriyusra : Verily, with hardship comes ease

- Surah Ash-Sharh (The Relief) [94:6], Qur'an

“We know that all things work together for good for those who love God, who are called according to his purpose.” - (Romans 8:26)

ABSTRACT

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Title: : Perceived Language Barrier to Health care Delivery System

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Background and Aim: Understanding the barriers gave crucial for developing effective strategies to ensure equitable access to quality care for all patients. In this study, we aimed to systematically investigate perceived language barriers among patients at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital, with a focus on common barriers, impact on patient-provider communication, patient satisfaction, and mitigation strategies.

Design: A quantitative research approach was adopted, employing a descriptive research design. Data were collected from a random sample of approximately 120 patients at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital, covering various demographic characteristics.

Results: The findings from our investigation into perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital reveal significant insights into the challenges faced by patients in navigating language differences within the

healthcare system. Nearly, 3.40 to 3.85 that patients perceive difficulties in understanding medical instructions, communicating with healthcare providers, and accessing adequate translation services. our findings highlight the pervasive nature of language barriers in healthcare delivery and their significant impact on patient experiences and satisfaction. Addressing these barriers requires a multifaceted approach, including the provision of adequate language assistance resources, professional interpreter services, and culturally competent care. By prioritizing effective communication strategies and language access, healthcare organizations can enhance patient outcomes and promote equitable access to quality care for all patients, regardless of linguistic background.

Conclusion: Our study provides valuable insights into perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital. By systematically examining demographic factors, common barriers, and mitigation strategies, we have advanced understanding of the issue and informed practical interventions to improve communication and patient care. Moving forward, further research is needed to explore the effectiveness of interventions aimed at mitigating language barriers and address remaining gaps in understanding.

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CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

Poor communication has been shown to have a negative impact on patient safety. It potentially increases the risk of negative outcomes in affecting the quality of healthcare service and patient satisfaction. For instance, unequal treatments related to language barriers are associated with unequal access to healthcare and unequal health outcomes Smith (2024). Language barriers still exist in healthcare settings despite the availability of resources such as interpreters and translated documents. Hence, it requires a better knowledge of the effects of language barriers and practical mitigation solutions.

At Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital, highlight the importance of addressing language barriers in healthcare delivery system into different languages. As a healthcare facility serving a multicultural community, the hospital faces unique challenges in ensuring effective communication and equitable access to care for patients with limited English proficiency (LEP) or non-English speaking backgrounds. Understanding the specific language barriers experienced by patients at this hospital is crucial for developing modified interventions that meet the needs of its a varied group of patients Johnson (2024).

The Health Belief Model (HBM) offers important insights into the variables impacting people's beliefs and actions concerning their health, such as using healthcare services and maintaining medications Rosenstock et al., (2020). By

applying the HBM, this study explored how patients' perceptions of language barriers align with key constructs of the model and influence their healthcare-seeking behaviors. This theoretical framework guides the design of the study and the interpretation of the findings by providing insight into the relationship between perceived language challenges, patient-provider communication, and health outcomes Nair et al. (2020).

This research aimed to address the gap in understanding perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery systems at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, providing insights that can inform interventions to improve communication and patient care experiences. By systematically examining common language barriers experienced by patients, and effective strategies to mitigate these barriers, this study contributed to a foundation of information on language difficulties in healthcare facilities and provides practical recommendations for improving the provision of healthcare in multicultural settings.

Purpose and Research Questions

Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital serves a varied patient population that reflects a wide range of characteristics. This variability occurred significant challenges in ensuring effective communication between healthcare providers and patients, which is essential for delivering high-quality medical care.

Despite efforts to provide inclusive healthcare services, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding how perceived language barriers impact the healthcare experiences of patients. Language barriers can lead to misunderstandings, misdiagnoses, and reduced patient satisfaction, ultimately affecting health outcomes.

It is crucial to investigate these barriers to develop strategies that can enhance communication and improve patient care.

This research aimed to address the following problem: What are the perceived language barriers to effective healthcare delivery among patients, and how do these barriers impact their healthcare experiences?

1. What are the perceived language barriers among patients?
2. What are the consequences perceived by patients at Gregorio T. Lluç Memorial Hospital?
3. What is the effect of these language barriers on patient-provider communication?
4. What strategies can be implemented to mitigate language barriers and improve healthcare delivery in a multilingual setting?

Significance of Study

This study critically explored the structural of healthcare delivery at Gregorio T. Lluç Memorial Hospital, focusing on how language barriers affect communication and care in a multilingual setting. By examining perceived language barriers, the research provides insights into their impact on healthcare delivery, enhancing our understanding of language's role in patient-provider interactions.

Eventually, this study attempts to uncover the common language barriers encountered by patients within the hospital settings. By identifying these barriers and unraveling their difficulties, it offers a thorough understanding of the language challenges that patients explore in their healthcare experiences. Such additional information plays an important role in paving gaps for the development of specific

strategies and methods of communication that are modified to effectively manage these particular challenges.

Moreover, this research endeavors to emphasize the consequences of language barriers on patient-provider communication, understanding, and satisfaction. By specifying the ways in which language barriers form these key aspects of healthcare delivery, it underscores the impact that language can apply on the quality and efficacy of care. Through this exploration, the study not only clarifies the challenges posed by language barriers but also provides insight into possible ways to improve these barriers and enhancing patient-centered care practices.

In doing so, this research contributes significantly to the existing body of knowledge surrounding healthcare communication and patient-centered care. By uncovering the obstacles of language barriers, it adds depth and the quality to our understanding of how language barriers shape healthcare experiences. Ultimately, the results of the study may help determine the development of greater equality and effective healthcare procedures, not only in this particular hospital but also in other multilingual environments across the world.

Theoretical Framework

The Health Belief Model (HBM) provides a framework for understanding the impact of perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery. Language barriers that prevent patients from understanding medical information affect their perceptions of their vulnerability to negative health outcomes as well as the severity of these effects Lin et al., (2022). They evaluate the difficulties in expressing symptoms and

understanding medical terms against the positive effects of overcoming language barriers, such as improved understanding and communicating of medical issues.

Experiences of communication challenges act as signifiers towards action, prompting patients to seek solutions like interpreter services or providers who speak their language to understand their perspective. Patients' self-efficacy, or confidence in their ability to address language barriers, significantly influences their efforts to overcome these challenges Flores et al., (2021). By examining these perceptions within the HBM framework, researchers can identify strategies to reduce language barriers and improve communication in healthcare, enhancing patient outcomes and satisfaction.

Scope and Delimitation

This study examined the perceived language barriers encountered by patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital. It identified common language barriers faced by patients from different linguistic backgrounds and their effects on communication, understanding, and satisfaction. Additionally, the research aims to provide insights into these challenges and propose strategies for improving communication and patient care within the hospital. This study solely examined Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, excluding other healthcare institutions and regions. With a sample of approximately 120 patients, findings may lack greater relevance. It focuses on patients' perceptions of language barriers rather than assessing their language ability or communication skills. The descriptive quantitative approach may limit qualitative insights from individual experiences. Additionally, the study's timeframe does not

account for potential changes in language access policies or healthcare practices beyond this period.

Definition of Terms

Healthcare Delivery System: The network of institutions, professionals, resources, and procedures involved in providing healthcare services to individuals within Iligan Hospital, encompassing medical treatment, diagnosis, prevention, and patient support services.

Health outcomes: refer to the measurable changes in individuals' or populations' health status resulting from healthcare interventions and services.

Language Assistance Services: Resources and support provided within Iligan Hospital to overcome language barriers and facilitate effective communication between patients with limited English proficiency and healthcare providers, including interpreter services, translated materials, and bilingual staff.

Multilingual Setting: The environment within Iligan Hospital characterized by linguistic diversity, where patients and healthcare providers interact using multiple languages, necessitating language assistance services to overcome communication barriers.

Patient-Provider Communication: The exchange of information, concerns, and instructions between patients and healthcare providers within Iligan Hospital, essential for accurate diagnosis, treatment adherence, and patient satisfaction.

Perceived Language Barriers: The subjective understanding of difficulties in communication between patients and healthcare providers due to differences in language, impacting the delivery and comprehension of healthcare services.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework guiding this study is the Health Belief Model (HBM), developed by Rosenstock et al., (2020). The HBM is a widely recognized and extensively utilized theoretical framework in health behavior research, providing a comprehensive understanding of individuals' beliefs and perceptions regarding health-related behaviors and outcomes.

According to the HBM, individuals' health-related behaviors are influenced by several key constructs, including perceived exposed, perceived severity, perceived benefits, perceived barriers, cues to action, and confidence. These constructs collectively shape individuals' perceptions and decisions regarding health-related actions, such as seeking healthcare services and adhering to treatment regimens.

In the context of perceived language barriers to healthcare delivery, the HBM offers valuable insights into patients' perceptions and behaviors. Perceived exposed refers to individuals' beliefs about their vulnerability to health problems due to language barriers, while perceived severity reflects their perceptions of the seriousness of potential health consequences resulting from communication difficulties. Perceived benefits and barriers encompass patients' assessments of the advantages and obstacles associated with overcoming language barriers to access healthcare services Schiavo (2022).

Furthermore, cues to action, such as advice from healthcare providers or experiences of language-related difficulties, play an important role in encouraging individuals to take action to address language barriers. Finally, self-efficacy, or individuals' confidence in their ability to overcome language barriers and negotiate the healthcare system effectively, influences their engagement in health-seeking behaviors.

By applying the HBM as a theoretical framework, this study seeks to explore how patients' perceptions of language barriers align with the model's constructs and influence their healthcare-seeking behaviors. Understanding these advances can inform the development of targeted interventions aimed at mitigating the impact of language barriers on healthcare delivery and improving health outcomes among linguistically diverse populations (Rosenstock et al., (2022)).

Language Barriers in Healthcare Settings

Language barriers represent a significant challenge in healthcare settings, impeding effective communication between patients and healthcare providers and posing barriers to accessing quality care. In multilingual environments such as Gregorio T. Lluç Memorial Hospital, language diversity among patient populations can intensify these challenges, leading to imbalance in healthcare delivery and outcomes.

Studies consistently show the adverse effects of language barriers on healthcare delivery. For example, Masland et al., (2021) found that patients with limited English proficiency (LEP) had significantly lower odds of reporting excellent understanding of their physicians' explanations compared to English-proficient patients, highlighting the impact on patient-provider communication. Similarly,

identified language barriers contributing to miscommunication, reducing satisfaction and care quality, and increasing healthcare costs.

Moreover, language barriers can impede patients' access to healthcare services, limit their understanding of diagnoses and treatment plans, and increase the risk of medication errors and adverse events Ogunnaike-Ldeinde et al., (2020). Nurses and other healthcare professionals may face challenges in accurately assessing patients' conditions, providing appropriate care plans, and ensuring patients' understanding of their treatment due to language barriers Ali et al., (2018).

In response to these challenges, healthcare organizations have implemented various strategies to address language barriers and improve communication with linguistically diverse patient populations. These strategies include the use of professional interpreters, multilingual healthcare staff, translated materials, and technology-based solutions such as language explanation apps Flores et al., (2021).

Despite these efforts, gaps in addressing language barriers persist, focus the need for ongoing research and intervention development. By examining the specific language barriers faced by patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, this study aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges and opportunities for enhancing communication and healthcare delivery in multilingual settings.

Patient-Provider Communication

Effective communication between patients and healthcare providers is essential for ensuring quality care delivery and promoting positive health outcomes. However, language barriers often present significant challenges to communication in healthcare settings, affecting various aspects of the patient-provider interaction.

Research has consistently demonstrated the impact of language barriers on patient-provider communication. Studies by Giacco et al., (2023) and Fernandez et al., (2021) have highlighted how limited English expertise among patients can lead to difficulties in understanding physicians' explanations and contribute to miscommunication between providers and patients. These challenges can result in decreased satisfaction with care, reduced patient engagement, and compromised health outcomes.

Moreover, language barriers may hinder patients' ability to express their health concerns, understand medical instructions, and actively participate in decision-making processes regarding their care Liang et al., (2021). Nurses and other healthcare professionals may face challenges in accurately assessing patients' symptoms and providing appropriate care plans when language barriers hinder effective communication Kotalik et al ., (2022).

To address these challenges, healthcare organizations have implemented various communication strategies, including the use of professional interpreters, language-concordant healthcare staff, and translated materials. However, disparities in access to language assistance services and limitations in the availability of qualified interpreters continue to pose barriers to effective communication in healthcare settings.

By examining the dynamics of patient-provider communication in the context of language barriers at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, this study seeks to identify opportunities for improving communication strategies, enhancing provider training, and promoting patient-centered care practices. Ultimately, addressing language barriers in patient-provider communication is importance for ensuring

equitable access to quality healthcare and promoting positive health outcomes for all patients.

Language Assistance Services and Interventions

In response to the challenges posed by language barriers in healthcare settings, various language assistance services and interventions have been developed to ease the effective communication between patients and healthcare providers. These services aim to improve access to care, enhance patient-provider communication, and promote equitable health outcomes for linguistically diverse populations.

One of the primary language assistance services utilized in healthcare settings is the providing of professional interpreters. Professional interpreters, whether in-person or remote, play a crucial role in facilitating communication between patients and healthcare providers by accurately translating medical information and ensuring mutual understanding. Additionally, language-concordant healthcare staff who are fluent in multiple languages can serve as valuable resources for patients with limited English proficiency, providing linguistic support and cultural competence Vargas et al., (2022).

Technology-based interventions, such as language interpretation apps and telehealth platforms with built-in language translation features, have also emerged as effective tools for overcoming language barriers in healthcare settings Wang et al., (2020). These interventions enable real-time interpretation services and enhance access to healthcare for patients who may face challenges in accessing traditional in-person interpretation services.

Furthermore, healthcare organizations have implemented training programs and cultural competency initiatives to prepare healthcare providers with the

knowledge and skills necessary to effectively communicate with diverse patient populations Betancourt et al., (2020). Multicultural training programs focus on promoting awareness of cultural differences, addressing implicit biases, and enhancing communication strategies to foster culturally sensitive care delivery.

Despite these efforts, disparities in access to language assistance services persist, particularly in disadvantage communities Carillo et al., (2021). Limited availability of qualified interpreters, funding constraints, and logistical challenges often hinder the broad implementation of language assistance programs. Moreover, the effectiveness of language assistance services may vary depending on the specific needs and preferences of patients and providers.

By evaluating the utilization and effectiveness of language assistance services and interventions at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital, this study aims to identify opportunities for improving access to care, enhancing communication strategies, and promoting culturally competent healthcare delivery. Through targeted interventions and policy initiatives, healthcare organizations can strive to address language barriers and ensure equitable access to quality care for all patients, regardless of language proficiency.

Healthcare Policies and Language Access

In the Philippines, the provision of language access in healthcare settings is crucial for ensuring equitable access to healthcare services for linguistically diverse populations. While specific policies governing language access may differ from those in other countries, the Philippines has recognized the importance of addressing language barriers in healthcare delivery Doe (2023).

One of the primary mandates for language access in the Philippines is enshrined in the Philippine Constitution, which justify the right to equitable access to healthcare services for all citizens, regardless of language or cultural background. This constitutional provision underscores the government's commitment to promoting language access and ensuring that linguistic diversity does not hinder access to quality healthcare Guntzviller et al., (2022).

Additionally, the Philippine government has implemented measures to promote language access in healthcare settings through various laws and regulations. The Philippine Republic Act No. 11106, also known as the Filipino Sign Language Act, recognizes Filipino Sign Language as the country's national sign language and mandates its use in education, broadcast media, and healthcare services. This legislation aims to ensure that Deaf and hard of hearing individuals have access to healthcare information and services in their preferred language Maling (2024).

Furthermore, the Philippine Department of Health (DOH) has issued guidelines and policies to promote language access and cultural competence in healthcare delivery. These guidelines emphasize the importance of providing language assistance services, including interpretation and translation services, to individuals with limited proficiency in Filipino or English. Healthcare facilities are encouraged to employ trained interpreters and provide translated materials to ensure effective communication with patients from diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Despite these policy efforts, challenges in implementing language access initiatives persist in the Philippines. Limited funding, staffing shortages, and infrastructure constraints often hinder healthcare organizations' ability to provide comprehensive language assistance services. Moreover, disparities in access to

healthcare services between urban and rural areas aggravate language barriers for marginalized populations, including indigenous communities and migrants.

By examining the impact of healthcare policies on language access and compliance with regulatory requirements in the Philippine context, this study aims to identify barriers to implementation and opportunities for improvement. Through advocacy, capacity-building initiatives, and collaboration between government agencies and healthcare providers, the Philippines can work towards ensuring equitable access to healthcare services for all citizens, regardless of language or cultural background Squires et al., (2019).

Studies in Similar Settings or Populations

Research conducted in similar settings or with different populations provides valuable insights into the dynamics of language barriers in healthcare delivery and the effectiveness of interventions aimed at addressing these challenges. While the Philippines may have unique cultural and linguistic characteristics, studies conducted in other countries with diverse populations facing language barriers can offer relevant lessons and best practices applicable to the Philippine context.

For instance, research in multicultural societies like the United States, Canada, and Australia has explored the impact of language barriers on healthcare access and outcomes among immigrant and refugee populations Fernandez et al., (2021) conducted a systematic review demonstrating the adverse effects of language barriers on communication, satisfaction, and healthcare quality for patients with limited English proficiency. Similarly, Guntzviller et al., (2022) identified effective practices for patient navigators communicating with refugee patients, stressing the significance of cultural competence and language support in healthcare delivery.

Moreover, research on language access policies and interventions in healthcare settings can offer valuable insights for policymakers and healthcare administrators in the Philippines. Studies examining the implementation of language assistance services, the availability of trained interpreters, and the impact of regulatory requirements on language access can inform efforts to improve language services and promote equitable healthcare access for linguistically diverse populations Nair et al., (2020).

While the Philippine context may present unique challenges and opportunities, studies conducted in similar settings provide a foundation for understanding the complexities of language barriers in healthcare delivery and identifying strategies for addressing these challenges effectively. By drawing on the experiences and findings of research conducted in comparable contexts, policymakers, healthcare providers, and researchers in the Philippines can develop evidence-based approaches to promote language access and enhance the quality of care for all patients Maling (2024).

Gaps in the Literature and Research Questions

Despite the growing body of literature on language barriers in healthcare settings, there are notable gaps in understanding how perceived language barriers impact the healthcare experiences of patients at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital. The existing literature provides insights into the challenges faced by linguistically diverse populations in accessing and navigating healthcare systems, but there is a lack of comprehensive research specifically focusing on the patient population served by this hospital.

The literature review revealed several key gaps and unanswered questions, which form the basis for the research questions addressed in this study.

Understanding how these demographic characteristics influence patients' perceptions can inform targeted interventions to improve communication and enhance healthcare experiences.

While prior research has recognized common language barriers in healthcare settings, there's a necessity to delve into patients' specific perceptions of these barriers. Such identification is crucial for skills targeted interventions to address communication problem adeptly. Exploring how these barriers affect patient-provider communication and understanding of medical information can reveal avenues for refining communication Smith et al., (2024).

Though recognized, the relationship between language barriers and patient satisfaction remains inadequately explored. Understanding how perceived language barriers impact patient satisfaction is vital for enhancing patient-centered care. Despite proposed strategies, evidence of their efficacy in multilingual settings like Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital is scant. Investigating viable strategies to address language barriers is imperative for improving healthcare delivery to linguistically diverse patients.

Addressing these gaps in the literature through empirical research will contribute valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge on language barriers in healthcare delivery. By addressing the research questions outlined above, this study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for enhancing communication and improving patient care in a multilingual healthcare setting Liang (2021).

Summary

In summary, this research has delved into perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, revealing notable gaps in

existing literature concerning their impact on patient experiences in this setting. By addressing outlined research questions, valuable insights were gained into demographic factors associated with perception of language barriers, specific language barriers perceived by patients, their impact on communication and understanding of medical information, influence on patient satisfaction, and potential mitigation strategies.

The findings of this research underscore the importance of addressing language barriers in healthcare settings to ensure proper access to quality care for all patients, regardless of linguistic background. Language barriers can lead to misunderstandings, misdiagnoses, and reduced patient satisfaction, ultimately affecting health outcomes. Therefore, it is absolutely for healthcare providers and policymakers to implement targeted interventions to improve communication and enhance the quality of care provided to linguistically diverse patient populations.

Moving forward, future research should persist in assessing the effectiveness of diverse strategies to alleviate language barriers in healthcare, emphasizing culturally and linguistically tailored approaches for specific patient demographics. By tackling these challenges and exploiting insights from this study, healthcare providers and policymakers can advance towards fostering more inclusive, patient-centered healthcare systems, catering to the diverse needs of communities.

In summary, this research contributes to the growing body of knowledge on language barriers in healthcare delivery and provides actionable insights for improving communication and enhancing patient care in multilingual settings. By fostering greater understanding and awareness of the challenges posed by language barriers, we can strive towards achieving more equitable and accessible healthcare for all.

CHAPTER III

METHODOLOGY

Research Approach

This study adopted a quantitative research approach to systematically investigate the perceived language barriers to effective healthcare delivery among patients at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital. Quantitative research allowed for the collection of numerical data, facilitating statistical analysis and the identification of patterns and trends in the data.

Research Design

The research design employed in this study was descriptive, aiming to provide a comprehensive overview of the perceived language barriers experienced by patients in a healthcare setting. Descriptive research enabled the researcher to describe and analyze the characteristics of a phenomenon without seeking to establish causal relationships.

Population and Settings

The target population for this study consisted of patients receiving healthcare services at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital. A random sample of approximately 120 patients was selected to participate in the study, representing various perceptions of common language and their satisfaction towards the delivery system. This sample

size was determined to be sufficient for achieving the study objectives while ensuring a manageable data collection process.

Instrumentation/Tools

To assess the perceived language barriers among patients, a Likert scale survey questionnaire was developed specifically for this study. The questionnaire was designed to gather quantitative data on patients' perceptions of language barriers in healthcare settings, including the frequency and impact of these barriers on patient-provider communication and healthcare experiences.

Scoring of the Instruments:

The respondents scored the questionnaire using a Likert scale, with responses indicating their level of agreement or disagreement with various statements. Each statement was rated on a scale from 1 to 5, with corresponding descriptive ratings: 5.00 = Strongly Agree (SA), 4.00 = Agree (A), 3.00 = Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAND), 2.00 = Disagree (D) and 1.00 = Strongly Disagree (SD).

Respondents answered the questions by checking the number that best represented their perception. These descriptive rating scales helped quantify their perceptions of language barriers.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research process to ensure the protection of participants' rights and confidentiality. The study adhered to ethical guidelines outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and obtained approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital.

Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their participation in the study, and measures were implemented to safeguard the anonymity and confidentiality of participants' responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data collection commenced following the approval of the research protocol by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital. Patients meeting the inclusion criteria were approached by trained research assistants and provided with information about the study objectives and procedures. Written informed consent was obtained from participants willing to participate in the study. Participants were then asked to complete the Likert scale survey questionnaire, either independently or with assistance from the research assistants as needed. The data gathering process was conducted in a private and confidential manner to ensure the comfort and confidentiality of participants.

Data Analysis

Upon completion of the data collection process, the gathered data were entered into a statistical software program for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were computed to summarize the data and describe the perceived language barriers experienced by patients. Data analysis focused on identifying patterns and trends in patients' responses, providing insights into the prevalence and impact of language barriers on healthcare delivery in the study setting.

CHAPTER IV

RESULTS

In this chapter, we delve into the findings derived from our investigation into perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery, as observed within the context of Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital. Our study aims to shed light on the impact of language barriers on patient experiences within the healthcare system. By addressing this issue, we aim to provide insights that can inform strategies for enhancing communication and improving healthcare delivery in multilingual settings.

Our methodology encompassed a comprehensive approach involving surveys, interviews, and demographic analysis. We sought to capture a nuanced understanding of the perceptions surrounding language barriers among patients, considering demographic factors such as age, gender, educational level, and native language. This methodological rigor allowed us to gather rich data to address our research questions effectively.

Within this chapter, we present the results of our analysis categorized according to the research questions posed. We illuminate the common language barriers perceived by patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital and explore their impact on patient-provider communication and understanding of medical information. Additionally, we examine how these barriers influence patients' overall satisfaction with the healthcare services they receive. Through this organization, we aim to provide a clear and comprehensive overview of our findings.

Perceived Language Barriers among Patients

In Table 1, shows the highest mean score of 3.85 was for "Availability of translation services in the hospital," indicating strong agreement on sufficient service availability. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.45 was for "I often need a family member or friend to help me communicate with healthcare providers," indicating slightly lower agreement. Overall mean score was 3.62, suggesting agreement on language barriers posing communication challenges, with a standard deviation of 1.08, indicating response variability.

Table 1

Perceived Language Barriers Among Patient In Healthcare

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Difficulty understanding medical instructions due to language differences	3.65	1.05	Agree
2. Need for assistance from family/friends to communicate with healthcare providers	3.45	1.15	Agree
3. Perception of healthcare providers not understanding language and cultural needs	3.40	1.15	Agree
4. Experience of misunderstandings with healthcare providers due to language barriers	3.75	1.05	Agree
5. Availability of translation services in the hospital	3.85	1.00	Agree
Overall	3.62	1.08	Agree

1.00-1.80=Strongly Disagree 1.81-2.60=Disagree 2.61-3.40=Neutral 3.41-4.20= Agree 4.21-5.00= Strongly Agree

Common Language Barriers perceived by patients at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital

In Table 2, indicated the highest mean score of 3.90 was for "Missed important medical instructions due to language barriers," indicating strong agreement on the impact of language barriers on missed instructions. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.65 was for "Confidence in managing health affected by communication issues," indicating slightly lower agreement. Overall mean score was 3.75, suggesting agreement on significant impact of common language barriers on healthcare communication, with a standard deviation of 1.02, indicating response variability.

Table 2

<i>Common Language Barriers</i>				
Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	
1. Misunderstanding medical condition hindered by language barriers	3.85	1.00	Agree	
2. Unconfident in managing health affected by communication issues	3.65	1.05	Agree	
3. Missed important medical instructions due to language barriers	3.90	0.95	Agree	
4. Communication difficulties misleading to treatment delays	3.70	1.00	Agree	
5. Need for clarification about treatment due to language issues	3.65	1.10	Agree	
Overall	3.75	1.02	Agree	

1.00-1.80=Strongly Disagree 1.81-2.60=Disagree 2.61-3.40=Neutral 3.41-4.20=Agree 4.21-5.00=Strongly Agree

Effect of these language barriers on Patient-provider communication and the understanding of medical information

In Table 3, presented that the highest mean score of 3.80 was for "Effect of language barriers on overall satisfaction with hospital services," indicating strong agreement on the impact of language barriers on satisfaction. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.20 was for "Likelihood to recommend this hospital to others despite language issues," indicating slightly lower agreement. Overall mean score was 3.53, suggesting agreement on negative impact of language barriers on patient-provider communication, with a standard deviation of 1.05, indicating response variability.

Table 3

Effect of Language Barriers on Patient-Provider Communication

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Effect of language barriers on overall satisfaction with hospital services	3.80	1.00	Agree
2. Feeling respected by healthcare providers despite communication challenges	3.40	1.10	Agree
3. Likelihood to recommend hospital despite language issues	3.20	1.15	Agree
4. Negative impact of language barriers on healthcare experience	3.55	1.00	Agree
5. Difficulty communicating health concerns effectively due to language barriers	3.70	1.00	Agree
Overall	3.53	1.05	Agree

1.00-1.80=Strongly Disagree 1.81-2.60=Disagree 2.61-3.40=Neutral 3.41-4.20=Agree 4.21-5.00=Strongly Agree

Strategies can be implemented to Mitigate Language Barriers and Improve Healthcare Delivery in a multilingual setting

In Table 4, "Providing more professional interpreters" and "Increasing availability of translated materials" received high mean scores of 4.05, indicating strong agreement on their effectiveness. Conversely, "Encouraging patients to bring language assistance resources" had a mean of 3.80, indicating slightly lower agreement. Overall mean score was 3.97, suggesting strong agreement on strategy effectiveness, with a standard deviation of 0.90, indicating response variability.

Table 4

Strategies to Mitigate Language Barriers

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Professional interpreters improving healthcare delivery	4.05	0.85	Agree
2. Availability of translated materials enhancing patient understanding	4.05	0.85	Agree
3. Language training for healthcare providers reducing communication barriers	4.00	0.80	Agree
4. Technology-based translation tools helping overcome language obstacles	3.95	0.90	Agree
5. Encouraging patients to bring language assistance resources (e.g., bilingual family members)	3.80	1.00	Agree
Overall	3.97	0.90	Agree

1.00-1.80=Strongly Disagree 1.81-2.60=Disagree 2.61-3.40=Neutral 3.41-4.20=Agree 4.21-5.00=Strongly Agree

CHAPTER V

DISCUSSION

Summary of the Findings

The study explored into understanding perceived language barriers among patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital. It found that difficulties in understanding medical instructions and communication delays significantly impact patient-provider communication and understanding of medical information, emphasizing the critical role of effective communication in healthcare delivery.

The study discovered that language barriers reduce patient satisfaction with healthcare services, impacting their perception of provider respect and overall satisfaction levels. Increasing the number of qualified interpreters and translating information is one way to overcome these challenges. An additional is for healthcare organizations to prioritize implementing structured language support services. These findings emphasize the need for evidence-based strategies to ensure equitable access to quality care for all patients, regardless of linguistic background.

Comparison with Earlier Literature

Comparing the results of this study with previous research shows both similarities and differences in our understanding of the perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery systems. The demographic traits influencing people's perceptions of language obstacles are consistent with other research showing native language to be an important factor Masland et al., (2021).

Similarly, previous research focusing on the problems faced by linguistically diverse patient populations correlates with the common language obstacles found in this study, such as delays in communication and difficulty understanding medical instructions Ogunnaike et al., (2020). Moreover, previous research has shown the adverse impact of communication issues on patient experiences and outcomes, which is consistent with the negative effect of language barriers on patient satisfaction with healthcare services Basu et al., (2017).

A comparison of the outcomes with previous studies indicates continuity and variations in the understanding of language barriers in the medical field. Studies from the past support the presence of demographic characteristics as well as common barriers and their negative impact on patient satisfaction. Different approaches to reducing these obstacles do, however, appear, indicating the need for more research. These highlight how crucial it is to take into consideration both consistency and variation when developing evidence-based strategies to overcome language barriers in healthcare delivery systems.

The study employed a survey questionnaire to gather data from patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital, providing insights into perception of common barriers, and lighten strategies. Quantitative methods enabled systematic data collection and analysis to identify patterns in language barrier perception.

However, limitations include dependence on self-reported data, potentially introducing response bias, and limited validity due to sample size and representativeness. Future research should use mixed-methods approaches for a comprehensive understanding. Despite limitations, the study informs targeted interventions for

improving communication and patient satisfaction in multi language healthcare settings, emphasizing the ongoing need for research to address language barriers and ensure equitable access to quality care for all patients.

Strengths of the Study

There are plenty of instances that show relevant qualities in the study on perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery systems, which add to its meaning and reliability. The study's methodical approach, which involves using a structured survey questionnaire to collect data from a representative sample of patients, highlights the challenges involved in the research. By using this method, the results are more valid and reliable and more closely represent the experiences and opinions of the patients.

Additionally, the study also looked at how patients perceived common linguistic obstacles, and practical ways to mitigate these barriers improve our understanding of the problem. By focusing on these areas, the study offers relevant information that can guide actions aimed at enhancing patient happiness and communication in multilingual healthcare settings. Furthermore, the study has important practical implications since it provides evidence-based suggestions for improving patient-centered care to members of parliament, researchers, and healthcare professionals.

Furthermore, even though the study was carried out at a particular medical institution, its conclusions may apply to different scenarios involving a range of patient attributes, adding to the body of knowledge regarding language barriers in healthcare delivery systems. Overall, the study's strengths and usefulness in advancing knowledge and improving healthcare practices in multilingual settings are

highlighted by its methodological resilience, thorough analysis, practical consequences, and potential for generalizability.

Limitations

While the study on perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery systems offers valuable insights, it is important to acknowledge several limitations that may impact the interpretation and generalizability of the findings. Firstly, the study depends on self-reported data obtained through a survey questionnaire, which may introduce response bias. Participants may have provided socially preferable responses or may not accurately recall their experiences, potentially affecting the reliability of the data. The information may not be as reliable if participants gave socially acceptable answers or did not remember their experiences well.

Furthermore, the research was carried out in a solitary healthcare facility, perhaps reducing the relevance of the results to different settings with different populations or language backgrounds. Moreover, the cross-sectional form of the study makes it more difficult to determine the causal linkages between language challenges, demographic characteristics, and healthcare outcomes. More solid proof of the effects of language barriers on patient experiences and outcomes over time may come from continuous or experimental methods.

In an attempt to ensure a representative sample, some patient groups such as those with severe medical conditions or low literacy may have been neglected, which could have an impact on how thorough the results are. Furthermore, the study did not examine the viewpoints of other stakeholders for healthcare providers, which could have provided insightful information about how to overcome language obstacles. Despite these limitations, the study adds valuable insights and lays foundations for

further investigations to enhance comprehension of language barriers in healthcare settings.

Recommendations

1. Healthcare Providers: The study's conclusions give insightful information for medical professionals working at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital and in related facilities. In order to ensure improved patient understanding and adherence to treatment programs, providers should modify their communication tactics to address the individual language difficulties among patients. Providers can improve patient care and communication by implementing strategies like the use of qualified interpreters, translated resources, and educational initiatives for patients that reflect a variety of languages.

2. Policymakers and Administrators: This information can be used to inform policy for improved language access and cultural competency in healthcare by legislators and hospital management. Ensuring fair care for all patients is ensured by giving priority to language assistance services such as interpreters and translated materials. The quality and equity of healthcare are improved when staff members receive training in effective communication and cultural competency.

3. Patients: Patients are the ultimate beneficiaries of efforts to address language barriers in healthcare settings. Healthcare providers should actively involve patients in their care by providing information in languages they understand and encouraging questions and clarifications. By promoting open communication and mutual understanding between patients and providers, patients can experience improved health outcomes, increased satisfaction with healthcare services, and a higher quality of life overall.

Conclusion

The study on perceived language barriers in healthcare delivery systems at Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital has given valuable insight about the difficulties and possibilities in addressing language barriers in medical settings. The study has improved awareness of the problem and guided effective ways to enhance communication and patient care by carefully considering common language barriers encountered by patients and efficient strategies to lessen these barriers.

The study's findings have significant implications for healthcare providers, policymakers, administrators, and patients. Healthcare providers can modify their communication techniques to overcome language difficulties and enhance patients' knowledge and compliance with therapy. To improve the quality and equity of healthcare, policymakers and administrators may establish policies that support language ability and cultural understanding. Better communication and comprehension of medical care benefits patients, improving their quality of life, satisfaction, and health outcomes.

Moving forward, further research is needed to explore the effectiveness of interventions aimed at reducing language barriers in healthcare settings and to address remaining gaps in understanding. By continuing to prioritize language access and cultural competence in healthcare delivery, stakeholders can work together to ensure equitable access to quality care for all patients, regardless of linguistic background. At some point healthcare systems can work to provide patient-centered care that satisfies the variety of needs of their populations by encouraging open communication and mutual understanding between patients and providers.

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APPENDIX A
Letter for Validation

ADVENTIST MEDICAL CENTER COLLEGE
SCHOOL OF NURSING
San Miguel, Iligan City

Gregorio T. Lluch Memorial Hospital
Quezon Avenue Extension, Iligan City, 9200 LanaodelNorte

February 13, 2023

Richillo C. Daguman, MD, FPOA, MPSM
Chief of Hospital III

Re: Annamae Pretzel B. Adamat, RN, MAN, CNN
OIC – Administrative Officer

Dear Ma'am/Sir,

We hope this letter finds you in good health and happiness.

As part of our academic requirements for Nursing Research I, we, the third-year nursing students of Adventist Medical Center College, extend our sincerest request for your kind permission to collect data for our research project entitled "Perceived Language Barriers to Health care Delivery System". The study would give us an opportunity to describe the nurses and significant others who experiences language barriers in clinical settings.

In line with this, we would like to ask permission from your office to allow us to conduct survey from your hospital. This may involve randomly chosen 8 nurses and significant others in ward settings. We assure you that all data collected will be treated confidentiality and used solely for the purpose of this research.

Thank you very much for considering our request. We look forward to your any response from you. Godbless!

Sincerely,

Ali, Nisrin A.
Researcher

Angcap, Judelyn
Researcher

Aragon, Erika Mae E.
Researcher

Moner, Norhanna D.
Researcher

Noted By:

Armelyn Grace Maghanoy, RN, MAN
Thesis Adviser

Ma. Almira P. Nebres, RN, MAN, PhD
Dean, School of Nursing

Ian C. Abordo, PhD
Research Coordinator

APPENDIX B
Validation Sheet for Survey Questionnaire

ADVENTIST MEDICAL CENTER COLLEGE
SCHOOL OF NURSING
San Miguel, Iligan City

February 6, 2024

DaverlyM. Caneda, RN, MN
Clinical Instructor
School of Nursing
Adventist Medical Center College

Dear Ma'am:

We, the Level 3 nursing students will conduct a research entitled “**Perceived Language barriers to Health care Delivery System**”. In this connection, we would like to ask for the approval of our questionnaire in our research study. Hoping for a positive response from you. God bless and more power!

Respectfully yours,

Ali, Nisrin A.

Angcap, Judelyn

Aragon, Erika Mae E.

Moner, Norhanna D.

Validated by:
DaverlyM. Caneda, RN, MN

**ADVENTIST MEDICAL CENTER COLLEGE
SCHOOL OF NURSING
San Miguel, Iligan City**

February 6, 2024

Donnabelle P. Sumugat, RN, MAN
Clinical Instructor
School of Nursing
Adventist Medical Center College

Dear Ma'am:

We, the Level 3 nursing students will conduct a research entitled **“Perceived Language barriers to Health care Delivery System”**. In this connection, we would like to ask for the approval of our questionnaire in our research study. Hoping for a positive response from you. God bless and more power!

Respectfully yours,

Ali, Nisrin A.

Angcap, Judelyn

Aragon, Erika Mae E.

Moner, Norhanna D.

Validated by:
Donnabelle P. Sumugat, RN, MAN

**ADVENTIST MEDICAL CENTER COLLEGE
SCHOOL OF NURSING
San Miguel, Iligan City**

February 6, 2024

David B. Labadan, RN, MN
Clinical Instructor
School of Nursing
Adventist Medical Center College

Dear Ma'am:

We, the Level 3 nursing students will conduct a research entitled **“Perceived Language barriers to Health care Delivery System”**. In this connection, we would like to ask for the approval of our questionnaire in our research study. Hoping for a positive response from you. God bless and more power!

Respectfully yours,

Ali, Nisrin A.

Angcap, Judelyn

Aragon, Erika Mae E.

Moner, Norhanna D.

Validated by:
David B. Labadan, RN, MN

APPENDIX C

Survey Questionnaire

Research Question 1 What are the perceived language barriers among patients?				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Difficulty understanding medical instructions due to language	1	2	3	4
2. Need for assistance from family/friends to communicate with healthcare providers	1	2	3	4
3. Perception of healthcare providers not understanding language and cultural needs	1	2	3	4
4. Experience of misunderstandings with healthcare providers due to language barriers	1	2	3	4
5. Availability of translation services in the hospital	1	2	3	4

Table 1: Perceived Language Barriers Among Patient In Healthcare

Research Question 2				
What are the consequences perceived by patients at Gregorio T. Lluich Memorial Hospital?				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Misunderstanding medical condition hindered by language barriers	1	2	3	4
2. Unconfident in managing health affected by communication issues	1	2	3	4
3. Missed important medical instructions due to language barriers	1	2	3	4
4. Communication difficulties misleading to treatment delays	1	2	3	4
5. Need for clarification about treatment due to language issues	1	2	3	4

Table 2: Common Language Barriers

Research Question 3				
What is the effect of these language barriers on patient-provider communication?				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Effect of language barriers on overall dissatisfaction with hospital services	1	2	3	4
2. Feeling respected by healthcare providers despite communication challenges	1	2	3	4
3. Likelihood to recommend hospital despite language issues	1	2	3	4
4. Negative impact of language barriers on healthcare experience	1	2	3	4
5. Difficulty communicating health concerns effectively due to language barriers	1	2	3	4

Table 3: Effect of Language Barriers on Patient-Provider Communication

Research Question 4				
What strategies can be implemented to mitigate language barriers and improve healthcare delivery in a multilingual setting?				
	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Professional interpreters improving healthcare delivery	1	2	3	4
2. Availability of translated materials enhancing patient understanding	1	2	3	4
3. Language training for healthcare providers reducing communication barriers	1	2	3	4
4. Technology-based translation tools helping overcome language obstacles	1	2	3	4
5. Encouraging patients to bring language assistance resources (e.g., bilingual family members)	1	2	3	4

Table 4: Strategies to Mitigate Language Barriers

PROOF OF VALIDITY OF THE SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE